

INCREASING THE EFFICIENCY OF TEACHING FINE ARTS IN SECONDARY GENERAL SCHOOLS

¹Mamitaliev Ahmadjon Ganievich, ²Adkhamova Oltinoy Rafikjonovna

¹Member of the Union of Artists of Uzbekistan, Andijan State Pedagogical Institute, teacher of the specialty "Fine Arts".

²2nd year student of the Andijan State Pedagogical Institute of the direction "Fine Arts and Engineering Graphics"

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7743163>

Abstract. *This article analyzes a number of knowledge and skills that serve to increase the effectiveness of fine art classes in secondary schools, and also provides an extensive analysis and some recommendations on ways and means to increase the interest of schoolchildren in the fine arts, further develop their creative abilities, quickly develop desires and hobbies painting, the tasks facing the teacher, who occupies the main place in these processes.*

Keywords: *Uzbekistan, fine arts, education, school, skills, lessons, activity, nature, result, efficiency, teacher, children, students.*

The future of our planet, its well-being depends on what kind of people our children grow up to be!

Sh. Mirziyoyev

Today, one of the most important tasks of our society is a radical reform of the education system and the organization of quality education. In order for qualified specialists to graduate in our country, it is first of all necessary to give a good education to the younger generation, starting from school age. From the first days of independence, the issue of radical reform of public education in our republic, bringing it to the level of developed countries of the world, was put on the agenda. For this purpose, the Law of 1992 "On Education" was adopted. The implementation of the plan and activities specified in this document was considered a priority of state policy. As a result, along with all subjects in general education schools, the "Concept for the education of fine arts in general education schools" was prepared, which was approved by order No. 5-5 by the Collegium of the Ministry of Public Education of the Republic of Uzbekistan on May 5, 1993. As noted in this concept, the following factors were taken into account in its preparation:

- modern requirements for the formation of an Uzbek child in the conditions of independent Uzbekistan:

- to strengthen the introduction of education based on national culture and art; - taking into account the fact that Uzbekistan is an eastern country in the implementation of education and the introduction on this basis of appropriate changes in the content of art education;

- in the implementation of artistic education at school, focusing on strengthening children's thinking, creative attitude to work and thereby forming a high taste and culture;

- to orient children to the comprehensive acquisition of knowledge and skills in the visual arts at school, introducing a differentiated art education on this basis.

Having drawn the appropriate conclusions from the concept, work began on the development of state standard educational programs in fine arts, as a result of which 270 hours were planned for "Fine Arts and Artistic Creativity" for grades 1-4, 245 hours for "Fine Arts" programs 1-7. A 560-hour Visual Arts program was also developed for grades 1-8. These programs

were published in a large number of copies and put into practice. At the same time, during the years of independence, special attention was paid to the training of teachers of fine arts. In particular, by 2002, special faculties and departments began to operate in Tashkent, Bukhara, Namangan, Gulistan, Andijan State Universities, Nukus, Angren, Jizzakh State Pedagogical Institutes. In the educational institutions of Khiva, Denov, Shakhrisabz, Karshi, Samarkand, Kattakurgan, Jizzakh, Andijan, teachers of fine arts were also trained. As a result of the reforms, the methodological foundations of schools have been developed to improve classes and achieve efficiency, they perform an auxiliary function in the process of lessons.

The purpose of teaching fine arts is to develop children's observation skills, the ability to see objects, and the development of memory. It is known that more than 90% of the information received from the environment enters through the eyes, and the remaining 10% is absorbed through the ears, nose, mouth and other organs. These qualities are of particular importance in training the perception of being, as well as in studying the basics of art criticism and depiction from nature. It is known that primary school education is a special stage in the process of education and upbringing, and this period is the period of the most rapid development of the child's personality. Because in the period from 5-6 to 10-11 years old, the child's personality is in the period of maturation and adolescence, and this period in the child's personality is the most intense stage in the process of learning to see, observe, perceive, imagine and think. In many schools in our country, we are faced with the following problems. Since the subject of fine art is not taught by a specialist in primary school, students do not know what the subject of fine art teaches, about colors, what to pay attention to when drawing, what a palette is, teaching aids, unfortunately, they grow up without understanding lines, shapes, colors, primary colors and the need for sequential drawing, i.e. step by step.

The concept of art is broad and it is primarily associated with human emotions. This is why visual arts, like other art forms, can have a strong influence on people's emotions. Fine art reflects various events, relationships, scenes. People, observing works of fine art, express their attitude to the events, situations, beauties reflected in them and are influenced by them. The image of people, nature, events, things on flat or three-dimensional surfaces by various means is called fine art.

Fine art is one of the oldest types of art, which is widespread in different countries and is an integral part of the spiritual culture of mankind, enriches the world. It usually expresses a real event in artistic images, generalizing existing objects by imitating their natural forms, reflects the size and spatial arrangement of objects. The artist reveals his essence, expressing the time of the event, phenomena and state through the image. When drawing a person, the artist tries not only to make him look like the original, but also to convey his thoughts and feelings to the viewer. Whatever picture the artist starts working on, first he observes in detail, builds a composition and draws sketches, thus forming the basis of the picture. In fine art, the correct form, size, colors and balance of objects are important.

As for the visual arts at school, they can be conditionally divided into two parts:

1. The specific and specific tasks of fine art lessons are: teaching to see, perceive, understand and appreciate beauty in being and art; development of aesthetic and artistic taste; expansion of children's circle of artistic thinking; development of artistic creativity and imagination; introduce the theoretical foundations of fine art (chiaroscuro, color theory, perspective, composition); the formation of basic skills in painting, modeling, artistic construction; development of observation, visual memory, ability to guess, spatial and figurative imagination,

abstract and logical thinking; learning to read and understand pictorial and practical architectural works of art; arouse interest in art, teaching to appreciate and love it.

2. Additional tasks of fine art lessons: help in the knowledge of being, life; implementation of the ideology of national pride and national independence; moral (patriotic, international) in children; implementation of labor and physical education; attracting children to various professions and crafts.

Speaking about the purpose and objectives of the subject of fine arts, it should be noted that it is associated with almost all subjects taught at school, and has an effective impact on the assimilation of materials related to them. This is especially important in the lessons of reading, literature, geography, natural science, biology, history, mathematics, labor. Fine art is useful even for physics, physical education, chemistry, music. It should also be noted that, although the fine arts are aimed at the implementation of aesthetic education, it serves to increase the effectiveness of the lessons of moral, social, environmental and physical education. School classes in fine arts are determined on the basis of educational tasks. Each teacher should pay special attention to the observance of teaching and educational tasks when choosing teaching materials. Fine art textbooks are mainly of 4 types. These are painting on the subject itself, drawing from the imagination, decorative drawing, drawing on the topic. Painting a picture based on the thing itself and painting a picture from the imagination occupy a central place in art classes. The reason for this is that such practical exercises help students learn to work with imagination, with the shape, structure, color and other characteristics of objects of existence and their differences from each other. Drawing based on the thing itself. In practical drawing lessons, students are taught to draw different plants, flowers, trees, birds and even animals. Before starting to draw, they are taught to follow and conduct a deep analysis of the drawing object. This helps students to better understand being. These activities serve to strengthen the memory of the students. In addition to the fact that visual art textbooks help teachers, along with this, teachers have several other tasks. That is, in order to increase the effectiveness of fine art classes, one of the most important tasks for a teacher is to be able to interest students in the lesson. If students are not interested in the lesson, there will be no efficiency and results in this area. Therefore, the teacher's choice of interesting and meaningful topics when teaching fine arts will attract the attention of students and directly help them increase their interest in the lesson. It is no coincidence that when developing programs in fine arts, attention was paid to the selection of the most meaningful interesting topics recommended for drawing by children. However, it should also be noted that the results of research conducted in the field of art, and observations made in the classroom, show that the drawings drawn by students on topics of interest to them are different from others, they are written more meaningfully and beautifully than drawings drawn on the topic. Such drawings, drawn by students, are of particular importance in the drawing class. In drawing lessons on a particular topic, in order to increase the interest of students, it is important to teach them to describe interesting things. For example, for school-age students, learning to work on a painting on topics such as sports, fairy-tale characters and cartoon characters gives good results. That is, if we take a ball from sports equipment, children play with the ball almost every day, they know its shape and can imagine the process of playing sports. They will work with interest on the topic of sports in the process of drawing. Drawing on the theme of fairy-tale characters is also very useful for schoolchildren and especially for elementary school students. As children, parents buy more fairy tales for their children, and we know that in these books each fairy tale is presented along with pictures. Not only in fairy tale

books, but also in textbooks, many fairy tales are printed with a phased development of events with pictures. And for schoolchildren, drawing on this topic becomes very interesting. Since these themes are related to the daily activities of children, they are effective in artistic activities as well. It is not surprising that children are most interested in making pictures that depict vivid images. When organizing painting based on a particular subject, an important task of the teacher is to create still lifes using objects that are interesting to children, making the right compositions. In such classes, the endless drawing of plaster geometric shapes and household items can bore children and children may lose interest in the fine arts. Using objects of different sizes and colors will give good results when drawing. For example: apples, pears, pomegranates, watermelons, melons, tomatoes, bell peppers, cucumbers, porcelain teapots, vases, bowls and other similar items. Drawing the simplest and most interesting subjects increases children's interest in fine arts and is the first step to improve the quality of fine arts. In addition, in addition to paying great attention to the choice of subjects to increase the interest of elementary school students, it is important to pay attention to the children's perception of objects drawn, their visual abilities, children's abilities, education and training conducted in schools. Paying special attention to the implementation of educational tasks is an important factor in increasing the effectiveness of fine art classes.

Today it is impossible to achieve a good result without careful preparation for the lesson. The reason is that over time, innovations in science appear, new and effective teaching methods appear, and the teacher is required to show initiative, ingenuity. The reason is that art lessons are a factor that develops students' worldview, creativity and aesthetic views. During the lesson, the teacher pays special attention to each student, taking into account his knowledge and level. , if necessary, he should deal with students who have difficulty learning the lesson, individually. This will certainly help in achieving the desired result. It is necessary to have close and good relations with students, to have a heart-to-heart conversation with them. It also happens that in the classroom the children fight with each other, and the teacher, instead of solving the problem in a good way, gets nervous and scolds the students, which negatively affects the students' progress. In this situation, the teacher must find the right way out. It is also necessary to distract children from fights and focus their attention on the lesson. With the help of various visual aids related to the topic, using various games, to attract students to the lesson and make the lesson more interesting. It also depends on the qualifications of the teacher. The specificity of teaching fine arts in the primary grades is determined primarily by age characteristics, psychology, interest, knowledge and skills of children studying in primary grades, and their combined abilities. The passion for drawing in children begins at the age of 2-3 years. It is more interesting for a child to draw than to read and write. But the duration of the pictures they draw is very short. 1 or 2 minutes, maximum 4-5 minutes. Although these drawings, made by children, are not complete, they express something in terms of content. In children of different ages, they end in different ways. It depends on age and skill level. To make the drawing lesson for school-age children even more interesting, learning to draw with paints gives a good effect. It is difficult for them to work with paints, but working with different colors is of great interest to them. When students don't get a beautiful drawing, they may feel frustrated. Showing the successful aspects of his drawing to students helps the child come out of depression. One of the characteristic aspects of the drawing process of elementary school students is that they try to simplify the depicted pictures. They describe only the front view, for example: a person, a clock, a TV, a book, and a house. Some drawings are described from above,

that is: a butterfly, a leaf, a telephone. The main reason for this is that children of this age cannot fully imagine the state of objects and objects and do not understand the rules of drawing.

The expediency of teaching fine arts in secondary schools was developed by the great Czech teacher J. A. Komensky in his work "Great Didactics". Noteworthy are the ideas of the French scientist J.-J. Rousseau on the improvement of painting in the system of general education. In his book "Emil or education" he proved that painting by nature is of great importance in the knowledge of being. In his opinion, it is more effective to paint in nature. Because children visually see things in nature in their true colors, perspective reductions and consciously understand its laws. Among European teachers, I. V. Goethe (Germany), J. G. Pestalozzi, I. Schmidt and P. Schmidt (Switzerland), A. Dupuy and F. Dupuy (France) made a great contribution. Teachers N. Pestalozzi, P. Schmidt, I. Schmidt defended the advantages of geometric methods over natural ones in drawing in general education schools. As a result, two currents appeared in teaching drawing in schools, based on two opposite natural and geometric methods. The advantages of painting from nature were supported by A. Comenius, J. J. Rousseau, J. V. Goethe, J. G. Pestalozzi, I. Schmidt and P. Schmidt, F. Dupuis tried to justify the geometric method.

While increasing the effectiveness of the lessons of fine arts for schoolchildren and educating the aesthetic perception of students, special attention is paid to children's perception of colors in nature. Children are taught not only to know the names of colors, but also to be able to see them, look for beautiful color combinations around them. The teacher shows the children trees in which branches and leaves have sprouted, and notes that the young leaves are light green, of a delicate color. After a spring rain, it emphasizes the purity of the leaves of the plant, they look like they have been washed, and the raindrops on them appear silvery. In the autumn nature, the yellow and reddish colors of the leaves of the trees have become golden, and the rustling of the "talking" fallen leaves is figuratively expressed. Children depict houses, trees, birds, animals, people, vehicles in their pictures. From here, without words, they encounter the sizes, proportions, textures, shapes and colors of objects and try to place them correctly in the composition of the picture. This prompts us to think about the proportionality, perfection, and appropriateness of their structure. Children think about what aspects of things and animals attract them in terms of shape and color, what side they look beautiful in, and what are their good and useful sides. When students think about things and events in nature, the teacher focuses on the beauty and perfection of the phenomena and events that match their understanding. Through wonderful experiences, he tries to teach children to be able to evaluate events and situations around him, awakens feelings of humanity, love for the Motherland, love for work. One of the most important tasks of fine arts lessons is to teach reading of works of fine, applied and architectural art. Fine art works reflect a certain content: fairy tales, stories, epics, novels. However, it cannot be read like a book. Fine art works have their own language. They can only be read by those who know them. In particular, artists reveal the content of the work with the help of such expressive means as lines, colors, sizes, composition, proportion, rhythm, symmetry, shape. In this regard, it should be noted that works of art, especially works of the historical genre, contain complete and comprehensive information about individual peoples and countries. Only those who know how to read them can deeply understand the ideas expressed in the works and the content described. They can also determine the artistic value of a work and give it an appropriate assessment. At the same time, they experience satisfaction and pleasure from such qualities as beauty, cheerfulness, heroism in creativity.

Conclusion

Any educational subject should be based on the incomparably rich cultural and spiritual heritage created by the Uzbek people. Therefore, it is necessary to teach the world-famous works of architectural, applied and fine arts of the Uzbek people more widely and deeply in schools than other materials. At the same time, it is advisable to classify the content of education in schools by regions and cities. Because the development of applied art and architecture in the regions, cities and even villages of Uzbekistan has its own uniqueness. This is clearly seen in the art of Bukhara, Samarkand, Kattakorgan, Rishton, Shakhrisabz, Nurata, Margilan, Gijduvan, Urgut, Khojaly and others. Our national art is our pride, and it is natural that we study it comprehensively. However, there are universal artistic values recognized by all peoples of the world. Without teaching them to students, our people cannot find their place in world culture. Otherwise, our students will not be able to enjoy the world's masterpieces, because they will be wrapped in a national shell. It should be noted that in addition to instilling relevant knowledge about our centuries-old national artistic culture (fine arts, arts and crafts, architectural art), students are given skills in fine and applied arts. Only then can we develop the worldview of young people and achieve efficiency in the subject!

REFERENCES

1. S. F. Abdirasilov. Tasviriy san'atni o'qitish metodikasi (Methods of teaching fine arts). Tashkent, 2012
2. B. Oripov. Tasviriy san'at va uni o'qitish metodikasi (Fine Arts and Teaching Methods). Publishing house "Ilm-Ziyo" 2005 Tashkent.
3. R. Gasanov. Maktabda tasviriy san'at mashg'ulotlarini takomillashtirish yo'llari (Ways to improve visual arts at school). Publishing house "Teacher", 1986, Tashkent.
4. R. Khasanov. Maktabda tasviriy san'at o'qitish metodikasi (Methods of teaching fine arts at school). "Fan" publishing house, 2004, Tashkent.
5. N. Saydakhmedov. "Yangi pedagogik texnologiyalar" ("New pedagogical technologies"). publishing house "Moliya", 2003, Tashkent.
6. B. Z. Azimova. "Natyurmort tuzish va tasvirlash" ("Still life composition and description"). Publishing house "O'qituvchi" 1984 Tashkent.
7. N. Abdullaev. San'at tarixi (History of Art) Volume 1. Publishing house "O'qituvchi", 1986, Tashkent
8. S. Abdirasilov. Tasviriy san'at o'qitish metodikasidan amaliy mashg'ulotlarni bajarish (Conducting practical classes on the methodology of teaching fine arts). 1996 Tashkent.
9. B. N. Oripov. Tasviriy san'atni o'qitishning zamonaviy pedagogik texnologiyasi, didaktikasi va metodikasi (Modern pedagogical technologies, didactics and methods of teaching fine arts). "Ilm- Ziyo" publishing house, 2013.